

Phf activation by HPV16 E7.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

East Islip, NY USA 11730

E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of *Phf1* and *Phf7* by HPV16 HPV E7.

Citations

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